

Kourion Episcopal Basilica and Urban Precinct

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Entry tags: Religious Complex, Orthodoxy, Religious Place, Christian Traditions, Religious Group, Early Christianity, Basilica

Located in the center of the Late Roman city of Kourion, the basilical precinct occupied a space just off of the old Roman forum. The basilica itself measured 39.95m by 22.88m and was situated above an older, civic building of the Roman basilical type. This older building furnished much of the limestone and marble building material, and spolia is much in evidence. Three aisled, but with only a single apse, the church is unusual amongst the early basilicas of Cyprus, which usually had three apses; this was likely due to the exigencies of making use of the footprint of the earlier building. The basilica and its attendant buildings were likely constructed under the tenure of Bishop Zeno, who attended the Council of Ephesus in 431, and served to replace the earlier, as yet undiscovered, basilica which was almost certainly destroyed in the major earthquake of 365 (the exact date of this earthquake is disputed). Replete with opus sectile and mosaic flooring (in addition to gypsum slabs), marble champlève revetment, carved marble column bases, and expertly carved marble ecclesiastical furniture, such as the ambo, the Kourion basilica must have been opulent indeed. Large quantities of mother-of-pearl tesserae point to an ornamental, as opposed to figural, wall decoration in addition to the floor mosaics. Small gold tesserae found near the apse point to the possible inclusion of a mosaic of the Theotokos at some point in the 6th c. To either side of the sanctuary stood two catechumena, which connected to the spacious narthex. These were meant to hold the unbaptized converts (the Roman Empire began converting en masse to Christianity in the 4th c.). To the Northwest and North of the basilica, respectively, lie an atrium and baptistry. Roughly 20m on a side, the paved atrium, with a central hexagonal cistern, featured small marble columns and was surrounded by a series of rooms on all but its East side (from which the baptistry was accessed). These rooms extended down to the West of the basilica and joined with a heavily mosaiced diakonikon and a small courtyard with a fountain. It is thought these formed the episkopeion, and many of the rooms also feature mosaic and marble decoration. These rooms, on two stories, would have accommodated the clergy. In the 6th century a second story was added to those rooms on the West end, extending above the diakonikon. A mosaic inscription in the floor of the diakonikon features a portion of a psalm relating to the leaving of gifts. In 1959 excavators uncovered the remains of a wall mosaic in the diakonikon that seems to feature the Theotokos and child, and an unidentified archangel. Coin evidence points to a date somewhere in the early 7th c. The three aisled baptistry, again with one apse, featured a cruciform font set into the South wall, and lavish mosaic decoration. Again, as with much of the precinct, renovation appears to have taken place in the early 7th c. In the mid-7th c. Kourion was subject to two Umayyad raids, and small traces of the cleanup have been found in the episcopal precinct, as well as a number of Arab and Arab-Byzantine coins that may date to the period of the Condominium. The end of the Kourion Episcopal Basilica can be attributed to a catastrophic earthquake at some point late in the 7th c. The southwestern portion of the narthex collapsed, and a diagonal wall was inserted to try and support the remaining superstructure. There are additional signs of violent seismic action in the structural remains. Coins at the site speak to continued activity into the 8th c., but at this point the basilica was dismantled and elements have been found at the nearby, and still occupied, village of Episkopi.

Date Range: 431 CE - 700 CE

Region: Kourion

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Cyprus

Site of Kourion in Cyprus

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Kourion: Excavations in the Episcopal Precinct. A. H. S. Megaw (ed.) 2007. Boston: Harvard University Press.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: .

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1934-1939, 1959-1960, 1974-1979

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Cyprus Expedition by the University of Pennsylvania University Museum (PUM), Excavation by the Department of Antiquities of the Republic of Cyprus, Dumbarton Oaks Center for Byzantine Studies Excavation

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: City is located on top of a cliff facing the sea

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: Centralized

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No single feature

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Although I describe here the entire precinct

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– Other [specify]: Deconstructed due to natural disaster

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Elements were taken to Episkopi to, one would assume, be used in the construction of a new basilica. That has not so far been definitely located, although elements have been found in the area of the later Cornaro manor.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: God/Christ

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– No

Notes: Here I'm referring to the possible veneration of the Theotokos at the site.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: Constructed by the church, with possible financial or bureaucratic assistance from the Roman state.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Possible

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: In the sense that you cannot have a church without scripture, in this case the Bible

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Yes

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

– No

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

– Yes

Notes: In the pastophoria.

↳ Space underneath the structure

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: .

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– Yes

↳ Are they read aloud:

– Yes

↳ To a human audience

– Yes

↳ Are they studied:

– Yes

↳ Are they recopied:

– No

↳ Used for divination:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: .

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Basilica is attached to the Baptistry, which is attached to the Atrium, which is attached to the Diakonikon and the Episkopeion. The entirety makes up the Episcopal Precinct.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: In a manner of speaking. The basilica is the central, and most important, building of the precinct, although all the others have their essential functions.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: I would say roughly half the precinct is composed of monumental architecture.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 914

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: Unlikely. I am referring here to the glass in the windows and the mosaic tesserae.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: I don't think it's been checked, but there is the possibility the roof tiles were made locally.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Almost certainly made from lime produced by burning spolia.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: Possibly imported.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Much of the island is composed of limestone.

– No

Notes: All marble had to be imported.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: .

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Glass, tesserae, and ceramic roof tiles had to be manufactured.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Carved decoration.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Carved champléve revetment, mosaic, opus sectile.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There likely would have been movable ecclesiastical furniture, icons, etc.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: In so far as Christ is Divine.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Archangels, for example the mosaic in the diakonikon.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints most likely, the Theotokos, definitely.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: .

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– No

Notes: Here I'm referring to that decoration that would have been contained in the sanctuary, behind the iconostasis.

– No

Notes: The vast majority of the decoration would not have been hidden.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Almost entirely floral.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Likely icons were present.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes
Notes: In so far as Jesus is a historical figure.

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: .

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: .

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There likely would have been one.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: .

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Opus sectile paving.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: In the form of the holy family.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: In reference to the crucifixion, annunciation, incarnation etc.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: .

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: Liturgies could be said for the dead.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: While burials are common under the side aisles of Early Christian basilicas, I don't think any have been located to date at this one.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: The Emperor is seen as the Vice-Regent of Christ on Earth.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: .

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: But possible.

↳ In dreams:

– No

Notes: But possible.

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the word of God is interpreted here via clerics.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: .

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the angels might be considered present.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: In the eucharist and wine/blood.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: But possible.

↳ In dreams:

– No

Notes: But possible.

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the words of Christ are interpreted by clerics.

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: .

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
– Yes

Notes: Must abstain from sin etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Performance of the liturgy is required.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: .

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: In the form of prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In that they can ask the saints or angels to intercede on their behalf.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense of tithing.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: .

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: If possible.

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

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↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: This takes the form of physical and spiritual cleansing, the latter through incense.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: .

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Yes

Notes: That is, baptism.

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Weddings.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Frequent, high holy days, name days, etc.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Large scale baptism was a central element in the overall design and construction of the precinct.

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– No

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
– number: Hundreds if not thousands.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– Yes

↳ Incubation
– I don't know

↳ Healing magic
– No

↳ Cleansing
– Yes
Notes: In the sense of expiation of sin.

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:
– I don't know
Notes: Possible, as this practice is current in Cyprus today.

↳ Expiation
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: .

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Baptisms, Funerals, and Mass.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Not all liturgies are attended by large numbers.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Baptisms, Weddings, and Funerals could be attended by hundreds if not thousands.
Average masses, unclear, possibly in the hundreds.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: There are seven fixed times for liturgy during a 24 hours period. Matins, Lauds, Prime, Terce, Sext, None, Vespers, and Compline.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Wine

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the number of worshippers the number of clerics required might rise or fall.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Notes: High holy days and harvest times would likely have required more staff.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that gifts to the church would almost certainly have included properties and revenues.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Notes: Almost certainly.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– I don't know

Notes: The church very well may have served this function within the community, particularly at times of duress.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: An ecclesiastical court would have functioned in the Episkopeion.

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: The church had its own cisterns and access to the aqueduct.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: .

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Lists of gifts and other documents/economic records.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

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- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - No

- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:
 - Yes

- ↳ Housed within the place/structure:
 - Yes

- ↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Probably.

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: .

Bibliography

General References

Reference: A. Megaw H. S.. Excavations at the Episcopal Basilica of Kourion in Cyprus in 1974 and 1975: A Preliminary Report.

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